

GIMNASTIKACHILARNING HAFTALIK O‘QUV- MASHG‘ULOT JARAYOLARINI TAHLIL QILISH

Termiz davlat pedagogika instituti

Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg‘ulotlar nazariyasi va metodikasi
mutaxassisligi 2-kurs magistranti.

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Tadqiqot dolzarbligi. Adabiyotlardan olingan ma’lumotlar tahlili bizni tadqiqot ishini tanlashga asos bo‘ldi. O‘smirlar organizmining funksional tizimlari ko‘rsatgichlarini, bazaviy jismoniy sifatlar va harakat ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirish jarayonini aniqlash bizning taxminimizcha yosh sportchilarni maxsus tayyorgarlik bosqichida sport - texnik maxoratini samarali o‘shishiga yordam beradigan qulay mashg‘ulot yuklamasi parametrlarini ochib beradi. Bizning fikrimizcha, mashg‘ulotning haftalik siklida «katta», «o‘rta» va «kichik» yuklamalarga farqlanishi, yosh gimnastikachilarni maxsus-jismoniy va sport-texnika tayyorgarligi samaradorligini oshirish, mashg‘ulot jarayonini shiddati darajasini aniqlash imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Tadqiqot vazifasi: IBO‘OZSM sharoitida yosh gimnastikachilarning tayyorgarlik amaliyotida qo‘llaniladigan mashg‘ulot yuklamasi xajmi va shiddatini aniqlash.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: yosh gimnastikachilarning musobaqa davridagi maxsuslashtirilgan tayyorgarlik bosqichida turli kattalikdagi va maqsadga yo‘nalitirilgan mashg‘ulot yuklamasini taqsimlashning samarali variantlarini ishlab chiqish va tajribalarda asoslab berish hisoblanadi.

Tadqiqot natijalari: tadqiqotda haftalik siklda mashg‘ulot yuklamasini xilma-xil navbatlantirishni o‘rganib chiqish xisoblandi. O‘tkazilgan tajriba maqsadi haftalik siklda katta, o‘rta va kichik hajm va shiddatlikdagi yuklamalarni qulay navbatlantirishni aniqlash.

Ta'kidlanganidek, ko'p sonli tadqiqotlar, hamda yuqori malakali gimnastikachilar tayyorgarligi amaliyoti, mashg'ulot yuklamasini o'zgaruvchan shiddatlik prinsipiga ko'ra qo'llanilish samaradorligini ko'rsatdi. Shu bilan birga yosh gimnastikachilar tayyorgarligi amaliyotida bunday muhim uslubiyatdan har doim ham foydalanilmasligini yuqorida ko'rish mumkin. Shuning uchun, yosh gimnastikachilar tayyorgarligida haftalik siklning turli kattalikdagi yuklamalarni qulay navbatlantirishni aniqlashga urinib ko'rildi.

Tajriba 3 oy davom etdi (2013 y. fevraldan - aprelgacha). Unda har biri 10 tadan (II razryadli) va 12 ta (I razryadli) uch guruh yosh gimnastikachilar ishtirok etdi. Har bir kvalifikatsiya guruhlaridan birinchi guruh quydagicha shug'ullandilar:

1-kun kichik yuklama, 2-kun o'rta, 3-kun katta, 4-kun kichik yuklama, 5-kun o'rta, 6-kun katta.

Ikkinchi guruh quydagicha shug'ullandilar: 1-kun o'rtacha yuklama, 2-kun o'rta, 3-kun katta, 4-kun kichik yuklama, 5-kun katta yuklama, 6-kun o'rta.

Uchinchi guruhda yuklama quydagicha taqsimlandi: 1-kun katta yuklama, 2-kun o'rta, 3-kun katta, 4-kun katta yuklama, 5-kun o'rta, 6-kun kichik yuklama.

Ko'rinib turibdiki, barcha guruhlarda yuklamaning aniq variantlari kuzatildi. Bu o'z navbatida, taqsimlanish samaradorligini aniqlash hamda organizmning alohida funksiyalarining har bir ishidan keyingi natijasini o'rganib chiqish uchun imkoniyat yaratdi. Ko'rinib turibdiki barcha ko'rsatkichlar bo'yicha ikkinchi guruh manfaatli ajralib turibdi.

Demak, dam olish kunidan keyin dushanbada kattaligi bo'yicha o'rta yuklamani bajarishda murakkab xarakterli harakat ta'siri natijalari deyaarli o'zgarmadi, qo'l panjasi dinamometriyasi o'sdi (statistik ishonchsiz). Maxsus chidamlilik ko'rsatkichlari ham o'sgan. Yurak qon-tomir tizimining funksional faoliyati ko'rsatkichlari ham ijobiy o'zgardi.

"Erkin mashqlar" testini bajarishda puls yg'indisi, maksimal puls, puls tiklanish vaqti va yurak qisqarish soni tiklanish davrida kamaydi. Buning hammasi,

yosh gimnastikachilar organizmi taklif qilingan yuklamani yaxshi uddalaganligini ko'rsatdi. Uchinchi guruhda aksincha, o'xshash ko'rsatkichlar keskin yomonlashdi. Bu yosh gimnastikachilar organizmi berilgan ishni qiyinchilik bilan o'tkazganligini isbotlaydi. Keyingi kungi barcha tadqiq etilayotgan ko'rsatkichlarning mashg'ulotgacha yomonlashgani, buni tasdiqlaydi. Bu bir kunda ham sinaluvchi organizmi tiklanmaganligini va taklif qilingan o'rta yuklama barcha ko'rsatkichlarni yomonlashuviga olib kelganligidan dalolat beradi.

Shu vaqtning o'zida seshanba kuni ikkinchi guruhda, hajmi va shiddatligi o'rta yuklama bajarilishi bo'sag'asida barcha ko'rsatkichlar yoki yaxshilandi yoki oldingi darajasida qoldi, taklif qilingan o'rta kattalikdagi ish esa ijobiy qo'zg'alishga olib keldi.

Dushanbada mashg'ulotni kichik yuklama bilan bajargan 1- guruh sportchilariga kelsak, bunday ishdan keyin ularning ko'rsatkichlari deyarli o'zgarmadi, seshanbada esa mashg'ulotgacha shu daraja saqlandi va ayrimlarida yomonlashdi. Bu haftaning birinchi kunidagi kichik yuklama ijobiy javoblar olib kelmadi va navbatdagi ishga yaxshi - ishchi xolat yaratmadi.

Tasdiqlandiki, seshanbada o'rta yuklama bajarilgandan keyin, murakkab harakat ta'sir vaqti, murakkab ta'sirlarda yo'l qo'yilgan xatolar, qo'l panjasi dinamometriyasi, statik va maxsus chidamlilik va ko'pgina ko'rsatkichlar mashg'ulot bo'sag'asida hamda undan keyin juda yomonlashdi.

Endi 2-guruhga qaytamiz, ikki kun davomida o'rta yuklama bajarish yaxshi funksional holatga olib keldi. Chorshanbada deyarli barcha o'rganilayotgan tavsiflar, dushanba kunga nisbatan mashg'ulotgacha yaxshi bo'ldi. Oxirgisi taklif qilingan katta yuklamani yaxshi uddalashga imkoniyat berdi. Albatta bu tabiiy, bunday ishdan keyin organizmda katta qo'zg'alish kuzatiladi, ko'pgina ko'rsatkichlar keyingi kuniga oldingi darajaga qaytdi. Ularga murakkab harakat ta'siri, statik chidamlilik, maxsus chidamlilik, "Erkin mashqlar" testida puls

tiklanish yg'indisi, vaqti va boshqa ko'rsatkichlar kiradi. Keyingi kuni (payshanba) kichik yuklamani bajarish, ko'pgina ko'rsatkichlarni yana ham yaxshilanishiga imkon berdi. Shunday qilib, murakkab harakat ta'siri, maxsus-chidamlilik ko'rsatkichlari chorshanbada mashg'ulotgacha bo'lgan darajaga yetdi, "erkin mashqlar" testi natijalari statistik ishonchli yaxshilandi.

Buning barchasi o'z navbatida, juma kuni katta yuklamani takrorlash taklif qilinganda, mashg'ulotgacha barcha ko'rsatkichlar meyorda bo'ldi yoki chorshanba kuni mashg'ulotgacha olingan ko'rsatkichlardan ancha oshib ketishiga olib keldi.

Yana uchinchi guruh ko'rsatkichlariga diqqat qilamiz. Haftani birinchi ikkinchi kunida bajarilgan katta va o'rta yuklama sal'biy qo'zg'alishga olib kelganligi aniqlangan edi. Yosh gimnastikachilarga taklif qilingan chorshanbada kichik yuklama ham vaziyatni to'g'rilamadi – mashg'ulotgacha va keyingi ko'pgina ko'rsatkichlar dushanbada mashg'ulotgacha belgilangan darajada qoldi, payshanba kuni bajarilgan katta yuklama juda ham yomon tomonga o'zgarishiga olib keldi. Birinchi guruh sportchilarida ham shunga o'xshash holat sodir bo'ldi.

Takidlab o'tilganidek, haftaning birinchi ikki kunida kichik va o'rta yuklamani bajarish yaxshi ishchi darajasini yaratmadi – barcha ko'rsatkichlar dushanba kungi darajada (mashg'ulotgacha) qoldi yoki juda yomonlashdi. Qolgan kunlarni mash g'ulotgacha tiklanmagan ko'rsatkichlarni keskin tushib ketishiga olib keldi. Ikkinchi guruhda esa aksincha, juma va shanbada katta va o'rta yuklamali mashg'ulot yaxshi natijalarni ko'rsatdi. Ko'rinib turibdiki, shanba mashg'ulotdan oldin va keyingi barcha ko'rsatkichlar, dushanba mashg'ulotgacha bo'lgan ko'rsatkichlarga nisbatan yaxshi.

Birinchi va uchinchi guruh sinaluvchilarining natijalari o'z kattaligi bo'yicha ikkinchi guruhdan past va qoida bo'yicha o'zaro statistik ishonchsiz farqlanadi.

Shunday qilib, haftalik mikrotsiklda mashg‘ulot yuklamasini eng qulay taqsimlanishi – bu ikkinchi guruh gimnastikachilarida qo‘llanilgan taqsimot deb xisoblashga asos bor.

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